

EDUCATION OF ETHNOCULTURAL TOLERANCE OF STUDENTS. THE CONTENT OF IMPROVING THE ACTIVITY OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK OF A HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the content of improving the spiritual and educational activities of the higher educational institution in the education of ethno-cultural tolerance of students.*

Keywords: *students-youth, ethno-cultural tolerance, higher education institution, spiritual and educational activities.*

Introduction. On the basis of the reforms implemented in our republic, attention is paid to concepts such as ethno-cultural tolerance, ethno-cultural solidarity and inter-ethnic harmony. In this regard, President Sh.M.Mirziyoev's decree "On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational work" defined the following: Solving existing problems, increasing the effectiveness and effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, increasing the scope and scale of in order to further expand, to strengthen the sense of belonging to the reforms being implemented in the hearts of the country's population, first of all, to the youth, to create a unified system of coordination of work in the field:

1. The following should be defined as priorities for the fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work:

To turn a healthy worldview and creativity into a national movement in society by widely promoting the idea of "From national revival to national rise" based on the principle of goodness and humanitarianism;

Ensuring the integrity of spiritual education in the family, educational organizations and neighborhoods;

Organization of activities in the direction of propaganda and education on a scientific basis, increasing the effectiveness of scientific and methodological research in the field, introducing a permanent monitoring system aimed at strengthening the stability of the social and spiritual environment;

Implementation of complex measures aimed at eliminating vices such as indifference to the fate of the country, localism, clannishness, corruption, disregard for family values and irresponsibility in the education of young people;

increase the population's culture of using the Internet global information network, strengthen their ideological immunity against ideological and informational attacks;

achieving the primacy of spiritual and moral criteria, national and universal values in culture, literature, cinema, theater, music and all types of art, publishing and printing products, mass media;

regular study of geopolitical and ideological processes, effective ideological struggle against terrorism, extremism, fanaticism, human trafficking, drug business and other dangerous threats, and development of international cooperation in this regard. [1]

In accordance with this decision, in all higher educational institutions of our republic, work is being carried out to bring the system of spiritual and educational work to a new level, to develop an innovative approach to students in the process of education.

Tolerance can become a value in the process of education and self-education of a person, forming a new attitude towards representatives of other ethnic groups and social communities, fighting against existing negative stereotypes, aggression. In this regard, the concept of "tolerance education" is analyzed.

Openness in knowledge and communication plays an important role in the process of education of tolerance. By instilling tolerance in students, it is necessary to teach them the ability to compromise while maintaining respect for others. Tolerance is a means of reaching an agreement in cases of increased ethnic, political, religious-ethical, ethnic conflicts. As it was repeatedly emphasized in the first chapter, tolerance does not mean being indifferent to the illegal manifestations of behavior and actions of one or another participant of the dialogue, regardless of nationality, confessional affiliation.

The process of education and upbringing in higher educational institutions is of great importance in the practical implementation of tolerance education in society. Educating in the spirit of tolerance is important for raising the dignity of a person, forming citizenship, peaceful coexistence of different peoples, different nationalities, different faiths, different political and other beliefs.

Analysis of literature on the topic: An important aspect of professionalism is the presence of certain professionally important characteristics in the personality of a teacher, among them reflexivity, empathy, and tolerance. One of the functions of tolerance in the process of professional pedagogical education is humanitarianism, the essence of which is the formation of values and interests of the future specialist "for the development of a spiritually rich person who can resist technocracy and inhumanity".

The research process showed that one of the most important tasks of universities is to educate tolerance. For this, it is necessary to create situations that ensure the development of restraint, obedience, and tolerance in students, and regulate their activities. Resilient education counters the effects of fear and alienation from others. Such education serves to form the skills of independent thinking, critical thinking and reasoning based on moral values in students.

In the implementation of the above tasks, a great responsibility is required from the teacher in the educational process. The most important task of the teacher is to learn to see and distinguish the first signs of a possible conflict situation and to prevent its further development or to find a way out of the conflict with compromise and tolerance. It requires to be achieved by directing spiritual and educational work with students during the educational process in educational institutions.

Taking into account the existence of threats to the stability of the state, students should be prepared to protect their homeland, country, material and spiritual wealth, people in all aspects of life, understand the danger of international terrorism, extremism and radicalism, their negative nature, correct in non-standard situations. Educating a morally mature person who can make decisions and is loyal to his duty and his country is of great pedagogical importance. For this purpose: - in the educational process, to form the skills of approaching the political and social processes taking place around us and the world based on our national interests, ideological immunity against various internal and external threats; - Inculcating the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the field of education, but also to be selfless for the country is a requirement of today, through real examples and effective means, it is important to inculcate in the minds of young people as priority tasks. [2]

In order to raise the spiritual and educational views of students, it is first necessary to increase the level of socio-cultural competence of professors and teachers, to create a tolerant socio-cultural environment in educational institutions:

Improving the qualification of pedagogic personnel, expressed in the form of preparing programs for courses through possible scientific and methodological support. It is important to emphasize that during this work, trainee teachers should develop didactic materials;

methodical approaches, that is, first of all, through seminars on the problems of the educational environment (both at the school base and at the regional, international level), it allows an active approach and a more detailed analysis of the specific features of the problem, taking into account its spatial and historical characteristics.

The environment of the university should be rich enough to encourage the student to develop himself, to reveal his creative potential, to increase his cultural level, and various technologies and forms of educational activity occupy an important place in it. The new environment of human life of the future affects all areas of education, determines the content of the educational environment aimed at acquiring skills, competences, future literacy in young people, including: concentration and attention management, ecological thinking, interculturality, learning and self-determination. Learning ability, creative, strategic, systematic thinking, communication, collaboration, self-regulation, financial, emotional, digital, legal and entrepreneurial literacy. It should be understood that students are active in all aspects of life. For example, a social network; the use of automation and robotics tools has not expanded; demographic changes are taking place; globalization is intensifying in the economic, technological, cultural environment; The very concept of "environmental friendliness" has been changed and defines not only the state of nature, but also the state of human life and industry.

Research methodology: Taking into account the existence of threats to the stability of the state, students should be prepared to protect their homeland, country, material and spiritual wealth, and people in all aspects of life, understand the danger of international terrorism, extremism and radicalism, and their negative nature, in non-standard situations. Education of a spiritually mature person who can make wise decisions and is loyal to his duty and his country is of great pedagogical importance. For this purpose: - in the educational process, to form the skills of approaching the political and social processes taking place around us and the world based on our national interests, ideological immunity against various internal and external threats; - It is important to inculcate the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the field of education, but also to be selfless for the country in the minds of young people through real examples and effective means. [2]

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The growth of spiritual and educational views of students is also important for their future professional preparation. This process is based on the development of personal characteristics.

It is important to carry out activities that ensure the spiritual and educational maturity of students.

- Formation of students' motivation for professional activity, self-development and self-education;

- identification and support of talented young people, their creative potential;
- organization, management skills, purposefulness, responsibility, personality formation;
- qualities necessary for a successful life;
- formation of socially important values and worldview, social skills system in students, familiarization of students with moral standards, national foundations and academic traditions;
- education of a person's internal need for a healthy lifestyle, responsible attitude to nature;
- inter-structural, inter-departmental organization and inter-university cooperation;
- formation of an information-educational environment that has a positive effect on the formation and development of the specialist's personality;
- forming the culture and ethics of professional communication, the culture of communication on the Internet;
- to educate the consciousness of tolerance and the culture of interethnic relations.

One of the conditions for the effective implementation of educational activities is the creation and development of an educational, social and cultural environment at the university. The environment is considered as one, an integral factor of internal and external psycho-social and socio-cultural development of a person, therefore, a young person acts as both an object and a subject of personal development. In general, the educational socio-cultural environment of the university is a system of spatial and subject environment, influence and conditions, and it is necessary to realize the possibilities of its development in order to form a highly cultured and competitive person in the modern labor market, which meets the educational goals.

Therefore, it is necessary to create organizational and pedagogical conditions that will help to form the professional competences of future specialists in the social sphere to work in a multicultural society in the conditions of a higher educational institution:

- 1) formation of the content and information supply of individualization of professional development of the future specialist, taking into account the mentality of a certain nation, nation or region and ethno-regional characteristics, taking into account the specific characteristics. In the professional training of specialists, taking into account the principle of multiculturalism (the ability to adapt to the mental characteristics of service consumers), social order and standard requirements, representatives of nationalities and ethnic groups living in this area in the social sphere, characteristics of the information-technological development of the educational environment;

2) to analyze the unique historical and socio-pedagogical situation of the social development of the region and the possibilities of its social environment, the national, regional and historical characteristics of the implementation of professional activities in the social sphere;

3) involving students in various activities that ensure the development of communicative skills in a multicultural society, forming their professional, social and personal competences;

4) to ensure the implementation of individual professional development of future specialists; [3]

Analysis and results. Organizing the celebration of Uzbek national traditions, national holidays, and ceremonies among students in each higher education institution is one of the main mechanisms for shaping the spiritual and educational outlook of students. Our national events give an opportunity to form feelings of goodness, patriotism, and humanity in the hearts of students. Studying and respecting the traditions, ceremonies, and activities of representatives of different nationalities in the process of performing spiritual and educational work from our national traditions, events, and ceremonies will stimulate the formation of interethnic tolerance in the minds of students.

The factors of raising national spirituality, national consciousness, national consciousness, and national feeling to perfection in every person are transferred to the process of activity. Our society has real opportunities to realize these ambitious goals. Selfless, hardworking, highly qualified forces with organizational potential are growing in our country. There is a stable core of national spirituality and creative power in their image and activity. Such people with stable national spirituality protect the interests of their people, nation, and homeland under any circumstances, they are able to demonstrate the national spirituality of our people in their activities, and they are able to show the potential of the nation, the value, honor, and fame of the Motherland between nations and countries. In other words, the cream of the nation's thinking is concentrated in such people and their activities have developed. That is why such persons, who have mature intellectual and intellectual intelligence, matured national spirituality, and have a strong sense of homeland and nation in their hearts, do not lose their identity when facing other cultures. A mature person is able to demonstrate the superiority of his spirituality and national culture. [4].

Spiritual and educational activities in higher education institutions are effective only when they are based on certain principles. Among the main principles determining the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work1:

- national ideological orientation;
- non-partisanship;
- education and training unit;
- vitality;
- integrity;
- unity of mind and behavior;
- practicality;
- publicity;
- encourage student initiative;
- encourage good qualities;
- fight against spiritual evils with "Enlightenment against ignorance";
- taking into account the future professional characteristics of students;
- unity is included. [4].

Constantly explaining to students the essence, importance and role of moral and ethical culture in pedagogical activity;

- widely introducing students to the rich spiritual and moral heritage of medieval Eastern thinkers, folklore, national education, spiritual and moral values;

- arming the subjects of the spiritual and moral education system with methods of improving the moral environment of students, academic groups, and higher education institutions; introducing the courses "Students - spiritual and moral education technologies", "Best practices of spiritual and moral education", "Student spirituality" for them. [4]

Conclusions and suggestions. Today, like all aspects of life, new attention is being paid to the field of education, especially to the education of young people.

The activities being carried out at the university to educate patriotic young people with high spirituality, independent thinking, and a firm life position are in accordance with the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's March 26, 2021 "Measures to fundamentally improve the system of spiritual and educational work" On the basis of the tasks defined in the decision of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, the Ministry of Health, the orders of the rector of the institute, as well as the regional and city hokims, the regional Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment, and the law-propaganda staff. , is being carried out in cooperation with representatives of religious offices, public organizations and others.

In connection with 5 initiatives by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to raise the spirituality of young people and organize their free time in a meaningful way, a plan of measures was developed in the institute based on a model methodical program of work to be carried out in the system of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. stands and wall exhibitions on 5 initiatives have been installed in all educational buildings and student residences.

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